

ADSORPTION AND KINETIC STUDIES OF LEAD (II) ION USING POWDERED SNAIL SHELL

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Abstract

Lead (II) ion was adsorbed from solution at regular time interval of 20 minutes for a total time of 130 minutes, using powdered snail shell by equilibrium sorption experiment using gravimetric method. Results show that 2.0g of the powdered snail shell was able to adsorb 9.97, 9.96, 9.95, 9.95, 9.79, 9.69 and 9.58 mg/L of Lead (II) ion, from initial concentration of 10mg/L, a similar trend was equally observed when the initial concentration of the Lead (II) ions was varied from 20mg/L to 70mg/L at different time intervals of 10, 30, 50, 70, 90, 110 and 130mins respectively. It was observed that the concentration of Lead (II) ion removed from the solution by the powdered snail shell depends on the contact time between the adsorbent and adsorbate. The results show that optimum adsorption was achieved at 110mins for 60mg/L metal ion solution. Adsorption was found generally to increase with concentration of adsorbate. It was observed that adsorption fits into the freundlich isotherm and pseudo second order kinetics.

KEYWORDS: Sorption; Adsorbed; Snail shell; Lead (II) ions; time intervals; Pseudo-second; Freundlich

INTRODUCTION:

Heavy metals by its nature have two most important characteristics, namely toxicity and persistency (Barnajee *et al.*, 2012).

Therefore disposal of waste containing these metals into receiving water bodies can be hazardous to both human and aquatic life. Reports have it that the presence of heavy metals in water pose serious problems, because they may be mutagenic and carcinogenic (Momcilovic *et al.*, 2011). Moreover they can also cause severe damage to human beings such as dysfunction of kidneys, reproductive system, brain and central nervous system.

Drinking water and wastewater are mainly contaminated by metal ions from different sources and this is a serious environmental problem (Akl and Ahmad, 2014).

Lead is one of the most common metals found in our environment.

It is usually extracted together with Zinc, silver and copper as ore, generally lead occur in the environment as a result of human activities, lead has a damaging effect to human health, it can found its way into human body through food(65%), water (20%) and air(15%). The maximum allowable lead content in safe drinking water is 0.25% (EPA, 2011), hence the need to have water and wastewater free of lead

Removal of heavy metals from wastewater in developed countries is normally achieved by advanced technologies such as ion exchange resins, vacuum evaporation, crystallization etc, However, in developing countries these methods cannot be utilized because of technical levels and insufficient funds (Mohammed *et al.*, 2005), hence it is required that simple and cheap methods of heavy metals removal from wastewater is utilized. Adsorption methods

using biomass is applied, lead can be removed from water or wastewater through different methods among which is adsorption.

This research focuses on the use of powdered snail shell (PSS), an agricultural waste that would have been a nuisance to the environment in the adsorption of lead from solution.

Adsorption studies show how adsorbate interacts with adsorbent. This gives the capacity of the equilibrium relationship between the adsorbent and the adsorbate, which are usually the ratio between quantity adsorbed and the remaining in solution at fixed temperature and regular interval of time.

Adsorption isotherm also known as equilibrium data are the fundamental requirement for the design of adsorption system.

Langmuir and Freundlich are the most frequent used adsorption isotherm in literature to describe the non-linear equilibrium.

The Langmuir is a theoretical isotherm developed in 1916. This isotherm is based on the following assumptions; all sites are identical and energetically equivalent, this implies that each site can hold an adsorbate molecule. Adsorption cannot proceed beyond a monolayer thermodynamically; the ability of the molecule to adsorb at a giving site is independent of the neighboring site for the adsorption of a solute from solution. The isotherm assumes uniform adsorption on the surface and no transmigration on the plane of the surface (Hall, *et al.*, 1996).

The Langmuir equation is given as $q_e = \frac{a_l k_l c_e}{1 + k_l c_e}$ (Valshnav, *et al.*, 2012), the linear form of

the equation is $\frac{1}{q_e} = \frac{1}{a_l} + \frac{1}{a_l k_l c_e}$, q_e = amount of the adsorbate (mg/g) on the adsorbent at

equilibrium (untreated wastewater), c_e = amount of adsorbate (ppm) at a particular temperature, a_l = adsorption capacity, k_l = energy of adsorption, a_l and k_l are obtained as

the slope and intercept from the graph of $\frac{1}{q_e}$ against $\frac{1}{c_e}$.

The Freundlich isotherm is commonly used to describe adsorption in heterogeneous surfaces; it's also used to estimate the adsorption intensity of the adsorbent towards the adsorbate. It was derived empirically in 1912 (Metcalf and Eddy, 2003). Freundlich isotherm can be expressed

as $q_e = K_F c_e^{\frac{1}{n}}$, where k_F = constant related to overall adsorption capacity (mg/g), $\frac{1}{n}$ = the

constant related to surface heterogeneity (dimensionless). A plot of q_e against c_e will yield a non regression line where $\frac{1}{n}$ and k_F can be determined, the value of $1/n$ ranges from 0 to 1,

the closer the value to zero, the more heterogeneous the adsorbent surface, (Zuwani *et al.*; 2009). It is also an indication that significant adsorption takes place at low concentrations.

Kinetics of adsorption: In adsorption, kinetic study is very important; this is to know the detail about the performance and mechanism of the adsorption. The solute uptake rate which determines the resident time required for the completion of adsorption can be obtained from kinetic analysis (Qiu *et al.*, 2009).

Adsorption kinetics is the base to determine the performance of fixed bed or any flow-through systems. Several mathematical models have been proposed to describe adsorption

data, these models can be classified as adsorption reaction models and adsorption diffusion models. Both models are used to describe the kinetic process of adsorption.

These models are however different naturally. Adsorption diffusion models are always constructed on the basis of the following three consecutive steps (Lazaridis and Asouhidou, 2003):

(1). Diffusion across the liquid film surrounding the adsorbent particles, i.e., external diffusion or film diffusion; (2) diffusion of the liquid contained in the pores and/or along the pore walls which is so-called internal diffusion or intra-particle diffusion; and (3) adsorption and desorption between the adsorbate and active sites, i.e., mass action.

Adsorption reaction models originating from chemical reaction kinetics are based on the whole process of adsorption without considering the steps mentioned above. Presently adsorption reaction models have been widely developed to describe kinetic process of adsorption (Banart *et al.*, 2003, Sun and Yang., 2003, Aksu and Kabasakal 2003). Three kinetic models, that is Lagergren first- order, pseudo-second order and intraparticle diffusion equations were considered to interpret the time dependent of the experimental data.

The Lagergren first- order equation is given as $\log(q_e - q_t) = \log q_e - \frac{k_p}{2.303} t$, where q_e and q_t (mg/g) are the adsorption capacity at equilibrium and time t (min), respectively. k_p (min^{-1}) is the pseudo-first order rate constant for the kinetic model.

Pseudo-second order kinetic model equations (Ho and Mckay, 1998) is giving as $\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{v_o} + \frac{1}{v_o q_e} t$ and $v_o = k_p^2 q_e^2$ where v_o (mg/g.min) means the initial adsorption rate and

the constant can be determine experimentally by plotting $\frac{t}{q_t}$ against t .

The intraparticle diffusion model equations (Chien and Clayton, 1980) is given as $q_t = k_{int} t^{1/2}$, where k_{int} is the intraparticle diffusion rate constant.

According to the above equation a plot of qt vs $t^{1/2}$ should be a straight line with a slope k_{int} when the intraparticle diffusion is the rate limiting step.

Due to its particular significant in adsorbent evaluations and applications, adsorption kinetic studies still attract considerable interest today, more deliberate and complicated models will be proposed on the basis of adsorption mechanism and diffusion analysis.

Contrast to the study of adsorption using activated carbon and different agricultural and animal by products, the study of powdered snail shell as an adsorbent is scarce, and the kinetic study of the treatment using this animal product is new. The only close information is on the use of chitosan in the treatment of wastewater (Zhiguang *et al.*, 2011). The snail shell cell wall is built in different layers each with a special purpose and built by a different cell layers (Aboua, 1995). The main shell layer which consist of a hard mineral aragonite (CaCO_3) is mechanically very hard and is very susceptible to chemical corrosion, on the other hand the skin shell though mechanically weak is quite unsusceptible to chemical corrosion, hence protect the shell layer (Poppe and Tagoro., 2006).

Aims and Objectives: This research work is aimed at finding alternative methods of removing lead (II) ions from water using locally sourced materials such as snail shell that may be environmental nuisance, the objectives is to use the powdered snail shell to adsorb the ions and determine the optimum time for the take up of this ions from solution.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Material collection: Disodium salt of ethylene diaaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), lead(II) nitrate ($\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$), Methyl red indicator were obtained from BDH, England.

The species of snail shell (*Archatina archatina*), collected from the environment within Ekpoma, in Nigeria were washed with hot water to remove sand and dirt, it was then sun dried.

Analysis of snail shell:

The snail shells were homogenized to fine powder, and sieved using a sieve of $0.5\mu\text{m}$ pore size to obtain fine powder. Stability test was carried out on the snail shell powder to know the pH at which it will dissolve in acid or alkali medium; this was done by preparing acid solution using 1M CH_3COOH and alkali solution using 0.5M NaOH , (Pearson, 1976).

All chemicals were of analar grade.

Analyses carried out on snail shell were: Protein, ash content, Nitrogen free extracts using standard methods and metals were analysed using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) (Bulk scientific model 210 VGP) after digestion (Burguera *et al*; 1986).

Analytical methods:

The method was complexometric titration using 0.01M solution of EDTA as titrant. Concentration was varied ranging from $10\text{-}70\text{mg/L}$ of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. Equilibrium sorption of Lead (II) ion on powdered snail shell was varied. 2grams of the powdered snail shell were introduced into a 250cm^3 conical flask containing 100cm^3 of the Lead (II) ion solution of varying concentration ranging from $10\text{-}70\text{mg/L}$. These were left for 10, 30, 50, 70, 90, 110 and 130 minutes to allow a state of equilibrium between the solid adsorbent and adsorbate. 25ml of the filtrate was titrated against 0.01M EDTA solution. The titration was carried out in triplicate and the mean value obtained.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The percentage adsorption was calculated using the formula $\frac{C_i - C_t}{C_i} \times 100\%$

Where C_i is the initial concentration of adsorbate and C_t is the amount adsorbed at time (t). the results of the percentage adsorption with time using 2g of the adsorbate is presented in Fig 1, below

Fig 1. Percentage adsorption against time

From the figure it was observed that the percentage adsorption was higher as the contact time increases. This is because the longer the time of interaction between the adsorbent and the adsorbate the better the adsorption, after the optimum time the adsorption reduces because the surface of the adsorbate will be saturated with the adsorbent hence poor adsorption. The efficiency of adsorption at different concentrations is shown in Fig 2, below.

Fig2: Percentage Adsorption against Concentration

Fig 2 showed that adsorption is high at low concentration. The efficiency of adsorption was high at low concentration, this is evident that as the concentration of the adsorbate increases the active sites of the adsorbent will be filled or covered with more than enough adsorbate hence reducing the efficiency of adsorption.

The Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherm were used to study the adsorption capacity of the powdered snail shell.

For Langmuir adsorption, the adsorption was studied at different concentrations (10,20,30,40,50,60,70)g, and the plot of C_0/C_t versus C_0 was drawn as shown below:

Fig 3 Langmuir Isotherm.

The values of Q_m , a and r^2 values are presented in Table 1 below

Table 1: Langmuir Isotherm data

$Q_m(\text{mg/g})$	-9.0×10^4	-2×10^4	-1.9×10^4	-1.6×10^4	-2.3×10^3	-1.3×10^3	3.4
A	9×10^3	2×10^3	1.8×10^4	1.6×10^4	2.3×10^3	1.3×10^3	31
R^2	0.26	0.57	0.80	0.65	0.46	0.42	0.37

The correlation coefficient (r^2) of the Langmuir isotherm indicates that the adsorption isotherm of Pb(II) ions adsorption from solution using 2g of powdered snail shell was not a good fit for the experimental adsorption data.

Freundlich adsorption isotherm was also applied to study the adsorption experimental data and the plot is shown in fig 4, below:

Fig 4: Freundlich Isotherm

The values of K , $1/n$ and r^2 are presented in Table 2, below:

Table 2: Freundlich Isothem data

K	0.011	0.011	0.004	-0.002	0.006	0.023	0.036
1/n	0.9	0.9	0.9	1.0	0.9	0.9	0.9
R ²	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999

Table 2, shows that the Freundlich adsorption isotherm for the experimental data of the adsorption of Pb(II) ions from solution using powdered snail shell was better fitted for the experimental data, since the correlation coefficient (r^2) values for all the data was 0.999.

The values of $1/n$ were almost unity for all the experimental data, indicating favorable adsorption. The results obtained were subjected to two kinetic models which are Langergrian or pseudo first order kinetics and pseudo second order kinetics.

The results obtained for the pseudo first order kinetic is presented in Table 3, below.

Table3: results of Pseudo first order kinetics

K ₁ (min ⁻¹)	84.0	128.5	127.0	310.1	159.96	145.4	220.4
R ²	0.901	0.738	0.826	0.956	0.788	0.902	0.931

These results were obtained at different initial concentrations of Pb(II) ions from 10mg/L to 70mg/L. from the table, it shows that the adsorption of Pb(II) ions from solution by powdered snail shell, did not quite fit into the pseudo first order kinetics, since the R² values at each concentration were below 0.999. the reason for this is that the equation differs generally from the true first order equation, since the parameter $K_i(q_e - q_t)$ does not represent the number of available sites, because it is mainly applicable to unilayer adsorbent (Akl and Ahmad, 2014).

The results of the pseudo second order kinetics are presented in Table 4, below:

Table 4: Results of the pseudo second order kinetics.

q _m	9.549	19.695	29.718	39.654	49.733	59.574	69.616
K ₂	1.494	0.490	0.246	0.140	0.081	0.162	0.144
R ₂	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999

The results were obtained from a plot of t/q_t against time in the pseudo second order equation. From the table it is observed that the experimental data fit the pseudo second order rate kinetics, since the R² values for each concentration is 0.999.

CONCLUSION:

From the experimental investigation, it is clear that powdered snail shell is a good adsorbent of Lead (II) ions from solutions and invariably from water and wastewater, the contact time was found to be effective on the adsorption process. The kinetic studies show that the adsorption process followed the pseudo second order kinetic model. Freundlich model showed the best fit for the experimental data. Hence in comparison with other adsorbent from literature it is can compete favorably with other available synthetic and natural adsorbents.

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